
EOSC-SYNERGY

Landscaping Country Report

The Czech Republic

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Abstract:

This landscape analysis report aims to provide an overview of the policies, practices, roadmaps, and strategies around funding, procuring, providing, accessing, and sharing of services and resources in the EOSC scope in CZ.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Aim and scope of this landscape analysis

This landscape analysis aims to provide an overview of the policies, practices, roadmaps and strategies around funding, procuring, providing, accessing and sharing of services and resources in the EOSC scope in the Czech Republic.

The landscape analysis focuses on research infrastructures, funders and e-infrastructures in the Czech Republic. It is based on online survey and desk research – face to face meetings, video calls and written communications with relevant subjects in the Czech Republic.

The survey was done using the SurveyMonkey survey platform. We implemented an online form based on [the list of questions implementing Pillar survey together with our additional questions](#) on national and international cooperation. We generated individual participants' links to all the participants. Using this link, the participants were able to continue in the interrupted filling of the form or repeatedly change the answers to the questions.

The individual link was sent to 48 research infrastructures in the Czech Republic (according to the [Roadmap of Large Infrastructures for Research, Experimental Development and Innovation of the Czech Republic for the years 2016–2022](#), including the national e-infrastructure e-INFRA CZ) in individual e-mail letters addressed to the official responsible person of the infrastructure. Completion rate was 48 %, the tables and graphs are according to 23 respondents answering at least 1 question.

We also conducted a desk survey of 11 research funding organizations in the Czech Republic.

1.2 Definition/delimitation of “EOSC compliant resources”

In the Czech Landscape on Research Infrastructures and e-Infrastructures, we identify these main categories:

1. research infrastructures,
2. national e-infrastructures,
3. funders.

The [Roadmap of Large Infrastructures for Research, Experimental Development and Innovation of the Czech Republic for the years 2016–2022](#) covers six disciplinary areas:

1. Physical Sciences,
2. Energy,

3. Environmental Sciences,
4. Biomedicine,
5. Social Sciences and Humanities,
6. ICT/e-infrastructures.

The identified and investigated research funding organizations are:

1. Czech Health Research Council (Agentura pro zdravotnický výzkum ČR)
2. Czech Science Foundation (Grantová agentura ČR)
3. Ministry of Agriculture of the CR (Ministerstvo zemědělství ČR)
4. Ministry of Culture of the CR (Ministerstvo kultury ČR)
5. Ministry of Defence of the CR (Ministerstvo obrany ČR)
6. Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the CR (MŠMT ČR)
7. Ministry of Industry and Trade of CR (Ministerstvo průmyslu a obchodu České republiky)
8. Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs of the CR (MPSV ČR)
9. Ministry of the Environment of the CR (Ministerstvo životního prostředí ČR)
10. Ministry of the Interior of the CR (Ministerstvo vnitra ČR)
11. Technology Agency of the Czech Republic (TA ČR)

1.3 Information sources on services, repositories, facilities and infrastructures

The [Roadmap of Large Infrastructures for Research, Experimental Development and Innovation of the Czech Republic for the years 2016–2022](#) together with the web pages of individual large research infrastructures referenced from the Roadmap and the [Ministry managed web pages on large research infrastructures](#) can be used as the information primary source.

The Roadmap of Large Research Infrastructures of the Czech Republic is a strategy document of the Czech Republic, which presents the policy-making approach of the Czech Republic to the large research infrastructures. In the international context, the Roadmap is equivalent to the [Roadmap of European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures \(ESFRI\)](#), being the Czech contribution to the landscape of research infrastructures constructed and operated in Europe and worldwide. The Roadmap and its amendments are formally approved by the Government of the Czech Republic.

The core part of the Roadmap consists of the presentation of 48 large research infrastructures of the Czech Republic, which are operated in the 6 scientific fields listed above. Beyond their basic characteristics, the Roadmap puts the individual facilities into the large research infrastructures' landscape and creates a map of unique research infrastructure capacities that are operated in the Czech Republic or partici-

pated by the Czech Republic and located abroad and made available to users on the open access policy basis.

The Landscape analysis on Research Infrastructures and e-Infrastructures identified the following main categories in the Czech Republic:

- The national e-INFRA CZ is a specific category “per se” as it is the one that represents the Czech Republic in all the EOSC-related “foundation” organizations and initiatives.
- The second category is represented by RIs that serve both as capacity and service providers and also consumers of their own thematics as well as general (future) EOSC services.
- The third category is represented by RIs who are “pure” service consumers, not adding any reasonable capacity and expecting others (their home institutions, e-INFRA CZ, free of charge capacity providers from abroad etc.) to cover their capacity needs.

1.4 International and EOSC related involvement

While such information is usually available as part of the description of each national RI, we asked all the survey participants to answer a question on their direct or indirect relationship to some large scale European research infrastructure (e.g. ESFRI one), which facilitates integrating their data and services into EOSC. As seen in section [Integration of data/services into EOSC](#), the majority of respondents are either not aware of any such participation or are not involved.

As we know from our own checks using the publicly available information, the majority of national RIs is connected to their international counterparts. We thus interpret this higher number of “No” answers among active participants of the survey as a result of rather low awareness of the EOSC related activities of their corresponding RIs.

We also asked our respondents on participation in the “standard” EOSC-related European e-infrastructures (EGI, EUDAT, PRACE). Only e-INFRA CZ, the national e-infrastructure, is participating in all of them, representing the Czech Republic (see section [Participation in selected EOSC-related European organizations](#)).

1.5 National policies and frameworks for open science support and collaboration

1.5.1 Formal regulations or publicly available policies

The national Open Access policy is handled by the Governmental Office for Science, Research, and Innovations (The Office). On February 28, 2014, Recommendations for Open Access issued by the Work-

ing Committee for Open Access chaired by professor Haňka were approved by the Office. The Committee recommends to adopt a Czech National Open Access Strategy in correspondence to the [European Commission Recommendation on access to and preservation of scientific information](#).

According to these policies:

1. Research organizations should:
 - cooperate on formulating and adopting national OA policy,
 - support an implementation of institutional repositories to archive research outputs and open data,
 - define responsibilities for researchers in terms of Open Access publishing.
2. Funding agencies should require open access to research output supported by the public budget.

On June 14, 2017, the *Czech National Strategy for Open Access to Research Information for 2017–2020* has been approved by the Government of the Czech Republic. The resolution commits the Deputy Prime Minister for Science, Research, and Innovation to work out an Action Plan for the Czech National Strategy for Open Access to Research Information.

On 29 April 2019, the Czech Government approved an *Action Plan for the Implementation of the National Strategy of the Czech Republic's Open Access to Scientific Information for 2017–2020*.

However, these activities deal primary with Open Access to the published material, just touching (if at all) the problem of Open and FAIR data.

The Czech Republic also has its representative in the OpenAIRE project. The Czech National Open Access Desk of the OpenAIRE project (NOAD-CZ) is supporting Open Science activities in the Czech Republic. NOAD-CZ members are part of the Czech government working group on implementation of the Action Plan of the National Strategy of Open Access.

There is a vivid community around Open Access topics based under the Initiative of Open Access of Association of Libraries of Czech Universities. More information can be found at <https://openaccess.cz/en/>. The initiative works for now as a main supporter for Open Access in the Czech Republic. There is also a newly established working group of „Open Access/Open Science Managers“ under this initiative, that should meet regularly and share practical knowledge about implementation of Open Access/Open Science at their institutions. This working group started its activity on 9. 3. 2020 and members are mainly from 11 Czech institutions that took part in the national support scheme for institutional development of Open Science based on actions taken by implementation of the mentioned Action Plan for the Implementation of the National Strategy of the Czech Republic's Open Access to Scientific Information for 2017–2020.

The National Information Centre for European Research is also active in dissemination of knowledge and support of Open Science. For more information please consult this link: <https://www.tc.cz/en/offers/national-information-centre-for-european-research>

There is also an active group supporting Creative Commons in the Czech Republic (members of NGO [Open Content](#)). This group is directly linked to the mentioned initiative of Assoc. of Libraries of Czech Universities, to the NOAD-CZ and also to the National Information Centre for European Research (National Contact Point for H2020). More about Creative Commons Czech Republic can be found here: <https://www.creativecommons.cz/> (only in Czech).

There is also an organization called CzechELib – National Centre for Electronic Information Resources responsible for dealing with academic publishers on the National level and newly founded High-level Action Group under the Research, Development and Innovation Council of Czech Government, that focuses on the national approach towards transformation for the Gold Open Access Model. At the national level, there is also an Action Group formed in 2019 responsible for implementation of the Action Plan for the Implementation of the National Strategy. More information can be found here: <https://www.vyzkum.cz/FrontClanek.aspx?idsekce=875884> (only in Czech)

The current president of European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers (Eurodoc) is also from the Czech Republic, Ms. Eva Hnátková (<http://www.eurodoc.net/eurodoc/eurodoc-board>), currently working for [National Library of Technology](#) (also the coordination facility for CzechELib).

1.5.1.1 Funders' Open Access Policy

It is funders who significantly contribute to the implementation of OA principles worldwide, e.g. Wellcome Trust in Great Britain, or National Institutes of Health in the USA. Such support is missing in the Czech Republic. One of the Czech the major funders, the Czech Science Foundation (GA CR), has signed the Berlin Declaration in 2008, however it does not explicitly require recipients to provide open access to their publications. In the Czech Republic, the European Union has become the key motivator in terms of providing open access to scientific outputs. The EU policy of open access to publications and research data in the current Horizon2020 program highly influences publishing practices and open access to scientific publications in all member states. There are expectations from the Czech expert Open Science community, that the implementation of Directive (EU) 2019/1024 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 June 2019 on open data and the re-use of public sector information into Czech legal environment can change this course in our country.

1.5.2 Strategies and policies for funding infrastructure services and resources

Research infrastructures and e-Infrastructures are funded in the Czech Republic through different means. The main institutions in the R&D system are the Research and Development Council, the Government Office for Science, Research and Innovations, the [Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports](#), and other administrative authorities responsible for R&D in their jurisdictions, government departments with their own budgetary chapters.

The Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports is the central body of state administration, among other things, for science policy, research and development, including international cooperation in this field.

[The Research, Development and Innovation Council](#) is an expert and advisory body of the Government in the field of research, experimental development and innovation.

[Czech ERA Portal](#) is an initiative of the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports and is operated in cooperation with the [Technology Centre of the Academy of Sciences of the Czech Republic](#).

Ministries: Ministry of Sports, Youth and Education is the primary responsible one, but own research oriented programs are also independently realized by other ministries, esp. Ministry of Health, Ministry of Culture, Ministry of Interior and Ministry of Industry of Trade. Special position has the Ministry of Regional Development, which oversees the ESF implementation.

The primary stakeholders responsible for the national research policy and its implementation are listed below. They interact in many formal and informal ways, and together they create a system that governs (but not implements) the research landscape in the Czech Republic. Only major stakeholders are noted.

The Research, Development and Innovation Council (R&D&I Council) is a professional and consultancy body of the Government of the Czech Republic in the field of research, experimental development and innovation. Its main tasks involve:

- Preparation of regular annual analysis of R&D&I and comparison thereof on the international level
- Processing of priorities of applied research, development and innovations of the Czech Republic
- Proposals for members of the Presidium and Chairman of the Technology Agency of the Czech Republic and the Czech Science Foundation

- A proposal for the size of overall expenditures on R&D&I of respective budget chapters and a proposal for their allocation
- Safeguarding and preparation of the Methodology for Evaluating Research Organizations and R&D&I Purpose-tied Aid Programmes
- Preparation of the National R&D&I and control of its realization
- Negotiations with the advisory bodies and councils for R&D&I of EC and other countries.

The Ministry of Sports, Youth and Education (MEYS) is the central body of the state administration of the Czech Republic for elementary, secondary and higher education, science and for the state's support for sports and youth. It has a responsibility over the preparation of the National Research and Development Policy of the Czech Republic in accordance with international treaties and the monitoring of its implementation in the form of positions on the compliance of the programmes of research and development presented by the providers with the National Research and Development Policy of the Czech Republic before these programmes are approved by the government. The MEYS manages the ESF funding for research, currently under the program "Research, Development and Education". The MEYS also coordinates funding for large research infrastructures and e-infrastructures, both from specific ESF and national funds; MEYS prepares the Roadmap of large research infrastructures which is approved by the government. The EOSC agenda is currently supervised by MEYS, too.

The Academy of Sciences Czech Republic with its almost 50 institutes has a separate budget chapter in the national budget. It also has its own funding agency, primarily to support fundamental research.

The research funding at the country level is also provided through two major funding agencies - The Grant Agency of the Czech Republic (GACR) and the Technology Agency of the Czech Republic (TACR). While the former primary target is fundamental and theoretical research and support of individual researchers and teams, the latter deals with applied research and specifically supports the collaboration with research institutions with industry. Both agencies operate with dedicated budgets approved by the parliament.

Additionally, individual ministries (esp. Ministries of Health, Culture, Interior, Trade and Industry and Transport) have programs to support research in their areas of interest.

At this moment, no coherent strategy towards Open Science (esp. Open Access and FAIR data) exists at the country level. However, preparatory work towards more aligned with EOSC vision and strategy in the next funding period (since 2023) is ongoing. This work is primarily coordinated by MEYS.

1.5.3 Present status with regard to Commission Recommendation (EU) 2018/790 on access to and preservation of scientific information

The recommendation sums up the current policy of European Commission towards Open Access to scientific information. The aim was to describe the overall policy of the institutions towards Open Access to scientific information. By scientific information the recommendation means both publications and data.

Most of the participants mentioned they are prepared to follow FAIR principles and, naturally, follow requirements of projects, such as EU H2020 requirements. However, many of them do not have any mandatory policy, do not provide data openly on the web, provide them mainly to the institution members or upon a request.

Multiple participants follow common practice of publishing scientific publications in topical repositories with metadata. Few of them have policies for publishing and managing research data. Some participants are concerned of legal issues connected with publishing/archiving publications in institutional/topical repositories.

The participants also expect national and European policies to adopt.

For example, participants responded:

“The infrastructure aims at fulfilling the compliance of data to the FAIR Principles. However, the data are openly available only to the Institute staff, to the university students supervised by the Institute staff, and to the external collaborators (Czech as well as foreign) solving joint projects with the Infrastructure.”

“The data access for other interested entities is granted based on a request that must be properly justified and then needs to be approved by the Infrastructure management.”

“There are no rules for Open Access to the scientific information now. The only rules are given for European projects where it is mandatory to publish the results in open access journals.”

“We publish data in peer-reviewed journals in the biology field. The data are then made public according to their requirements. Furthermore we send the data into publicly available repositories. We also share the publications on our web.”

1.6 Survey on Funders

The results from the funders’ perspective are available in the last section [Survey Results: Funders](#) of this document.

1.7 EOSC compliant resources

The survey results in the following sections of this document provide quantitative or semi-qualitative answers to the characteristics of the services and resources provided, including their FAIRification, DMPs and data management in general. They also cover other important aspects like the *services for EOSC*, the current status and challenges of the transnational offer of and access to their services (the section *Trans-national organisation/federation offering Service Level Agreements*), as well as problems and opportunities for the harmonization of national policies on joint procurement or coordinated service provisioning (see section *Obstacles of collaboration on services or hardware procurement*).

2 Survey Results: Research Infrastructures

2.1 Policies

2.1.1 Organisations imposing rules for funding on (internal) grant recipients concerning the various aspects

The participants of the survey were asked about the existence and type of requirements of the recipients of their grants in several areas related to Open Sciences. The summary of the results is shown in the following table and visualized in the graph.

	No encouraged regulation but optional	Mandatory, for some grants	Mandatory, not for all applicable grants	Mandatory, for all grants	No response
Open Access Publications	45,83%	33,33%	4,17%	4,17%	12,50%
Data Management Plans	66,67%	8,33%	4,17%	8,33%	12,50%
Open Research Data	62,50%	16,67%	0,00%	8,33%	12,50%
Long-Term Availability of Research Data	54,17%	16,67%	8,33%	8,33%	12,50%
Compliance of Data to the FAIR Principles	66,67%	12,50%	8,33%	0,00%	12,50%
Compliance of Data to the FAIR Principles	66,67%	12,50%	8,33%	0,00%	12,50%
Publishing Data in a Repository	58,33%	25,00%	4,17%	0,00%	12,50%

The results show it is not common among the survey participants to require Open Science-enabled handling of publications and data as a condition of granting grants. Some of them consider these requirements of low-priority in their research area (humanities) as they expect most of the research there not requiring hard data as the foundations of their research. One of the participants stated that: *“The rules are not applied now but we would like to apply the rules mainly for data management plan, open research data and long-term availability of research data.”*

It is also worth noticing that not all the investigated organizations are providing grants.

2.1.2 Status of organizations with regard to the Commission Recommendation (EU) 2018/790 on access to and preservation of scientific information

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The participants also expect national and European policies to adopt.

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“There are no rules for Open Access to the scientific information now. The only rules are given for European projects where it is mandatory to publish the results in open access journals.”

“We publish data in peer-reviewed journals in the biology field. The data are then made public according to their requirements. Furthermore we send the data into publicly available repositories. We also share the publications on our web.”

2.1.3 Buying of supplies, resources or services

The participants were asked on the methods of buying of supplies, resources or services.

Naturally, all of them follow law regulations that allow different buying procedures according to the type and value of the purchase. Most of the purchase is done with tender but many participants also use other possibilities given by the law.

Some purchases are done according to institutional/consortial regulations (such as ERIC procurement rules).

	Responses
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Not applicable	4,17%
Buy or rent without tender	54,17%
Buy or rent with tender	87,50%
Buy or rent on pre-negotiated procurement/tender	41,67%
Other (please specify)	8,33%
No response	0,00%

2.2 Services

2.2.1 Knowledge and granularity of the unit costs of services

The survey shows that roughly 50% of participants are aware of the unit costs of their service, some of them only per set of services. The rest of the participants do not have readily available this information, almost one quarter of all of them are even not able to calculate this information easily.

One of the respondents commented on this question: *“There is a unit cost per some services and we are in the process of having more services to be covered by the unit cost. However, currently there are too large differences in understanding what a ‘unit cost’ should/could include among funders to seriously work with ‘the unit cost’ widely accepted. And national funders don't work with a unit cost, instead providing capital investment directly.”*

	Responses
Yes, cost per service	41,67%
Yes, cost per set of services	12,50%
Not currently available, but could be calculated	20,83%
No, but in preparation	4,17%
No, not possible/not foreseen	20,83%
No response	0,00%

2.2.2 Type of services provided to the research community

The participants of the survey were asked what type of services they provide to the research community.

The participants selected from the list of multiple choices, one of the participants responded that they are collecting data in an open access regime to the research community.

	Responses
Knowledge-based resources such as collections, archives or research data	50,00%
Data and computing systems, and communication networks	33,33%
Major scientific equipment or sets of instruments	45,83%
No, none of this list	4,17%

Other (please specify)	0,00%
No response	0,00%

2.2.3 Services provided to the research community

In the next question, the participants were asked about particular services provided to the research community. Again, they selected from the list of multiple choices. The vast majority of them offer data infrastructures for storage and management of research data, some of them provide high-performance computing capacities to process the data. However, the list did not fit to all of the participants, for example:

“We are a research infrastructure, providing highly specialized analytical instruments. We are not an IT solution provider”

“Internal data infrastructure mainly is run by biobanks themselves...”

“The infrastructure does not primarily offer any of the services above in terms of research data, however, some of the facilities of the infrastructure partners can offer archival, transport or processing of research data.”

Only one participant provides high-bandwidth networks and other services:

“Environment for collaboration, videoconferences etc.”

	Responses
We offer data infrastructures which store and manage research data (e.g. archive and disseminate data).	66,67%
We offer high-bandwidth networks which transport research data.	4,17%
We offer high-performance computing which can be used to process research data.	20,83%
Other (please specify)	4,17%
No response	29,17%

2.2.4 Services of the participants considered to be possibly useful to be part of EOSC

The participants had the following opinions of services to be possibly useful to be part of EOSC:

“The use of ENREGAT infrastructure in pilot scale.”

“storage for sensitive data - omics and images mainly; possibly computational power for machine learning in future will increase”

“high throughput computing, data storage”

2.2.5 New services planned in the next five years

The participants were asked about services that they aim to introduce within the next five years. There was a variety of ideas:

“extension of analytical techniques”

“We plan to provide data related services for infrastructure users. These services will serve to transfer the data created in the scope of the research project only.”

“In the next five years' period, we plan to improve and enlarge our existing services. All steps of innovation relate to the core of our infrastructure.”

“The target of the research made in our RI is to sustain the current speed of decreasing the energetic demands of the economy, increase of energetic independence and improve the quality of the environment. The research goals aim for a higher rate of application of technologies and materials with minimal impact on the environment, implementation of biotechnologies into production and the use of biotechnologies in production of renewable sources of resources and energy. The research targets concentrate on ways to minimize waste and ways to reuse it. Another target is the development of activities (particularly of the basic oriented research nature) in areas, which have expected potential for use in energetics and enable to strengthen competitiveness and participation in international initiatives.

The key prerequisite of further development is also the creation of an effective education system, which will as much as possible react to the demands of the society, labour market and economy and will be interconnected with the labour market's demands.”

“Our infrastructure provides mostly services related to microscopic methods, sample preparation, (microscopic) data analysis. Planned innovations: Acquisition of the high-end instrumentation in the field of biomedical imaging, extending the portfolio of provided technologies and methods”

“high throughput computing, data storage, increasing the capacities and reliability”

In summary, all the participants want to keep up-to-date with technologies, efficiency and methods to be competitive.

2.2.6 Type of scientific disciplines the services are provided for

According to our survey, the majority of participants provide services for Natural Sciences. Other disciplines are less supported (STEM disciplines are preferred to humanities). One of the participants stated

they are supporting all the research disciplines: “Being a domain neutral e-infrastructure provider we serve users and communities of all scientific communities (and including use in education).”

	Responses
Natural Sciences	75,00%
Engineering and Technology	33,33%
Medical and Health Sciences	29,17%
Agricultural Sciences	20,83%
Social Sciences	16,67%
Humanities	25,00%
None / Not applicable	0,00%
Other (please specify)	4,17%
No response	0,00%

2.3 Funding/Revenues

2.3.1 Funders of the organizations

There are different providers of the recurrent funding to the participants’ organisations, but the majority of respondents are getting funds from the government sources and European funds. Many of them are also

getting funding from funding agencies and bodies or research institutions. Other funding sources are uncommon.

	Responses
Research institution(s)	54,17%
University	33,33%
State/ministry	83,33%
Region/town	4,17%
Research communities	4,17%
European funds	83,33%
Industry / small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs)	12,50%
Funding agencies / funding bodies	70,83%
Other (please specify)	0,00%
No response	0,00%

2.3.2 Own revenues other than funding

Besides funding, the organization can have its own revenues. According to our survey, roughly one-third of the research infrastructures have their own revenues, the rest depends on the funding.

The sources of “alternative” revenues differ, for example:

“Our infrastructure can acquire revenues from services which are provided within commercial research carried out by private enterprises.”

“We store samples and data sets for a long time and if these are provided to researchers for their research the biobank can ask for a refund of the storing costs.”

	Responses
Yes	37,50%
No	62,50%
Don't know	0,00%
No response	0,00%

2.3.3 Sources of own revenues from digital services

If participants have their own revenues other than fundings we asked for specification to these sources. The main source, according to the survey, are consulting and training services. Other sources are, for example:

“monitoring of clinical trials”

“Working for free for collaborating institutions.”

	Responses
Managed online services (software as a service, applications, storage, computing).	4,17%
Hosting (hardware and services for third parties).	4,17%
Consultancy or training.	12,50%
Other (please specify)	12,50%
No response	75,00%

2.4 Service Level Agreements (SLAs)

2.4.1 Offering of Service Level Agreements on digital services

The survey shows that the vast majority of the respondents do not think they can apply SLAs on themselves. Less than one-quarter of the respondents offer SLAs on (at least some) of their services. Few respondents consider offering SLAs in the near future. Some requirements on the services are given by the law requirements:

“Part of the operation is based on conditions set by legislation and related legal arrangements. Contracts are concluded with the organisations authorised to carry out archaeological research on the conditions for the use of the system.”

	Responses
Yes, for all service	8,33%
Yes, for some services	20,83%
No, but foreseen in the near future	4,17%
No, not foreseen in the near future	25,00%
Not applicable	45,83%
No response	0,00%

2.4.2 Types of Service Level Agreements on digital services

We also investigated what types of SLAs on digital services are respondents offering or will offer in the future – one generic SLA, set of predefined SLAs or custom made SLAs. Predefined set of SLAs is the most used option, only a minority of participants is able to offer one-fits-all SLA.

	Responses
Several predefined types	20,83%
Custom made type	12,50%
One-fits-all	4,17%

Not applicable	54,17%
Other (please specify)	0,00%
No response	8,33%

2.4.3 Issues with establishing Service Level Agreements

It seems only a minority of participants encountered issues or barriers to establish SLAs with a community:

“Not all institutions are willing to move to a digital form of communication. Some organisations have technical and organisational problems linked to the obsolescence of IT equipment, the lack of competence of staff and a reluctance to share their own data.”

“Only commercial partners/customers are actually prepared to seriously discuss and pay for the SLAs.”

	Responses
Not applicable	37,50%
Don't know	20,83%
No	29,17%

Yes (please specify)	8,33%
No response	4,17%

2.5 Access to Services

2.5.1 Restricting access to services

Some organisations grant all users access to their services, some limit access to their services based on certain criteria. According to our survey, some organisations restrict access to its services to defined groups of users, however, roughly 40% of them do not apply any restrictions. Some restrict commercial use or consider requests case-by-case:

“The services of the large research infrastructure are not provided to the private companies”

“The users are granted access on a case-by-case basis. The head of each facility approves the users who wish to perform their research at the given facility.”

“Access to data is offered only for non-commercial and educational purposes.”

“Metadata to samples available can be browsed by everybody. If the requestor has approval from ethical commission there is a higher probability that the biobankers will answer his/her negotiation via Negotiator.”

“So that instead of approving by funding bodies there is more important ethical commission.”

“We have different price for different kind of users (material, material + work, material+work+extra)”

“We distinguish different levels of accessibility based on the need to protect personal data, the agendas involved, copyright protection and the protection of archaeological heritage. However, most of the archived data is publicly available to all registered users.”

“Generally, we impose as few as possible access restrictions to national users -- all researchers and university students are allowed to use most of the services/resources by default, but there are services (e.g. access to HPC resources) where the access is restricted.”

	Responses
Not applicable	4,17%
No access restrictions	37,50%
Users or communities approved by the funding body (e.g. due to regional or research topic restrictions)	12,50%
Users selected by competition	16,67%
Members of certain communities or organisations (e.g. virtual organisations)	33,33%
National users	8,33%
Other (please specify)	12,50%
No response	0,00%

2.5.2 Barriers of expanding services to further users groups

We investigated organisations on the existence of policies, procedural and/or technical barriers that limit the expansion of their digital services to further user groups. Roughly half of them are aware of such barriers.

	Responses
Yes	41,67%
No	33,33%
Don't know	16,67%
No response	8,33%

2.5.3 Description of barriers of expanding services to further users groups

We asked for more detailed description of policies, procedural and/or technical barriers limiting the expansion of the digital services to further user groups.

“Policies based on manager realms. They are implemented by POSIX permissions.”

“The main barriers are the data storage capacity for research data”

“We have kind strict safety rules from our institute, so it is difficult to send data outside our internal network.”

“All of the data are freely open via open access.”

“Data is private and accessible only to collaboration members.”

“Access is limited to collaboration members.”

“No policies are applied within the infrastructure.”

“Personal capacities and financial resources”

“Unnecessarily broad interpretation of copyright in relation to the research outputs. Data on archaeological heritage and the results of primary field research should be exempt from copyright protection as part of cultural heritage.”

“Policies: data is owned by collaborations and only members can do a full analysis to publish papers. Subsets of processed data are made public.”

“The mission is limited to the academic sector.”

“Service offered to collaborating institutions.”

“In most cases, the use by commercial companies or general citizens (not researchers) is not allowed.; Funder's defined policies are the primary source of restrictions.; The insufficient capacity is the real barrier for expansion.”

2.6 Services Fees

2.6.1 Charging users/clients for services

Among our participants, the majority of them (almost 70%) do not charge their users/clients for the services the participants provide to them. If charges are applied then usually to the full portfolio of the services.

“The services are free of charge at the entry point, but we are providing some services to specific customers through contracts that include payment for the service. But in general, users don't directly pay for using the services provided.”

	Responses
Yes, for all services	16,67%
Yes, for digital services only	4,17%
Yes, for non-digital services only (use of special hardware devices, for example)	8,33%
No	66,67%
No response	4,17%

2.6.2 Method of charging users/clients for services

Methods of charging for services differ, some respondents said, for example:

“Price is set individually. Depends on concrete samples/data sets.”

“The charging is always custom made per the contract.”

	Responses
Based on a price list for individual items/services (e.g. use of datasets, certain storage capacity or virtual machines).	12,50%
Based on a flat rate for different sets of items/services.	8,33%
Solutions tailored to user needs.	29,17%
Other (please specify)	4,17%
No response	58,33%

2.6.3 Type of users of the services

Investigation of the type of users showed that not all respondents are tracking the type of users and frequency the usage of the services. If statistics are known, the investigation results are summed up in the following table:

	Portion of respondents serving the group	Usual frequency of use
(Researchers based at) universities	62,50%	Very often (daily)
(Researchers of) non-university research institutions	62,50%	Very often (daily)
(Researchers of) private, commercial institutions	41,67%	Rarely
Governmental institutions (e.g. census bureaus)	45,83%	Rarely
E-students		
Citizen scientists	37,50%	Very rarely or never
Professionals	29,17%	Occasionally
Other	20,83%	Rarely or never
No response	37,50%	

2.7 Services Policies

2.7.1 Public availability of access policy

Investigation of public availability of access policy for digital services or data showed that slightly less than one half of the survey participants have publicly available access policy.

	Responses
Yes	45,83%
No	50,00%
No response	4,17%

2.7.2 Plans for the publishing of access policy

Our survey showed that only a few participants are planning to publish the access policy in near future (less than two years), roughly 30 % of participants are planning to publish the access policy in the future.

	Responses
No	4,17%
Yes, in less than 1 year	4,17%
Yes, in 1 to 2 years	8,33%
Yes, in more than 2 years	12,50%
No applicable	54,17%
No response	16,67%

2.7.3 Authorization of the access to data

Methods of authorization of the access to data varies but individual authorization of access to datasets is the most common.

	Responses
Group membership: Members of groups can access all files open to the group.	25,00%
Mapping of group membership to the local file system.	12,50%
Access to datasets is authorized individually.	45,83%
Service local authorization: users choose with whom they share files, (e.g. NextCloud or Google Docs).	20,83%
No access control, data is openly accessible.	12,50%
Not applicable.	16,67%
Other (please specify)	12,50%
No response	4,17%

2.7.4 Services processing personal data

Our survey shows that only a few survey participants admit they offer services that process personal data in research data. The common procedure is data anonymization or pseudonymization, for example: *“Biobanks are usually part of hospital so that the personal data are pseudonymized several times before being sent to researchers. For clinical studies can be the personal data anonymized.”*

	Responses
Yes	20,83%
No	75,00%
No response	4,17%

2.7.5 Services processing special categories of personal data according to Art. 9 GDPR

In terms of processing personal data, the survey participants were asked whether their organisation offers digital services that process special categories (according to Art. 9 GDPR) of personal data in research data?

Personal data is defined as data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, genetic or biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health, a natural person’s sex life or sexual orientation.

Again, only few of them do so.

	Responses
Yes	16,67%
No	75,00%
No response	8,33%

2.7.6 Dissemination of research data

Research data are published under various licences among our survey participants. The majority uses some of the CC licences, roughly one third uses tailored licences.

However, some participants do not disseminate the research data:

“research data has not yet been disseminated”

“We do not disseminate raw research data”

“We do not disseminate data. We follow study protocol and consent on handling of personal data.”

“We do not disseminate research data.”

Several respondents told the licence depends on various factors and is decided on a case-by-case basis:

“The organization disseminate the research data through the dedicated data repositories related mainly to the research papers”

“This very much depends on the nature of the data. In general, we strive to be as open as possible, but as we are working mostly with copyrighted material, we are bound also by the copyright and agreements with text publishers.”

“it depends on the policy of the journal”

	Responses
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Public domain (Copyright not applicable, Public Domain Mark, Creative Commons: CC 0)	33,33%
Creative commons licences for open reuse (CC BY (Attribution), CC BY-SA (Attribution-Share Alike))	20,83%
Creative commons licenses for restricted reuse (CC BY ND (Attribution- NoDerivatives), CC BY NC (Attribution-NonCommercial), and combinations including ND or NC)	16,67%
We use tailored licences	20,83%
No response	37,50%

2.8 Services Federation / Authentication

2.8.1 Need of support to federate services to EOSC

Almost half of the participants of our survey expect they will need implementation support outside of their organisations to federate their service to EOSC. There were several ideas on the needed support:

“It would be great to have the possibility to share our raw data”

“Services are already included in EGI. Permanent support from outside is needed to be able to be a part of the EGI grid.”

“We are already connected. Continuous support to implement new technologies is required.”

“We interpret the answer as implying that federating the services will incur additional costs that must be covered somehow.”

	Responses
Yes	41,67%
No	4,17%
Don't know	45,83%
No response	8,33%

2.8.2 Authentication model of services

To authenticate users to use the services the respondents use a variety of services. Only a minority uses federated services of EGI (Checkin) or EUDAT (B2ACCESS), a notable portion of them use local au-

thentication or other solutions like LDAP, Kerberos, x509 certificates, SSO Shibboleth, VOMS (Virtual Organization Membership Service) servers, or local authentication with tokens; MFA.

	Responses
Member of a national federation	16,67%
Using EGI (Checkin)	8,33%
Using EUDAT (B2ACCESS)	8,33%
Local authentication (etc/passwd)	33,33%
Other (please specify)	29,17%
No response	29,17%

2.8.3 Plans for services authentication through an Identity Provider (IdP)

It seems the majority of the participants are satisfied with their current authentication model. Less than 30% of them are planning to authenticate their services using an Identity Provider (IdP)?

	Responses
No	4,17%
Yes, in less than 1 year	0,00%
Yes, in 1 to 2 years	12,50%
Yes, in more than 2 years	12,50%
Don't know	29,17%
Not applicable	33,33%
No response	8,33%

2.8.4 Use of eduGAIN

We asked our respondents whether their services are proxied to eduGAIN. It turned out a lot of them are not sure about that. Only roughly 5% use eduGAIN. Other solutions, like “*Directory and Negotiator*”, are also in use.

	Responses
Don't know	33,33%
Yes	8,33%
No, we don't use a proxy	41,67%
No, we use a different service provider-identity provider (SP-IdP) proxy (please specify)	8,33%
No response	16,67%

2.8.5 Local/external management of authorisation information

In order for digital services to become part of a federation, these services cannot rely on locally managed attributes only. Our survey shows the authorisation information is often managed locally at the service level as well as received from an external attribute authority. All the combinations are roughly equally popular.

	Responses
Attributes are managed locally	12,50%
Attributes are received from an external authority	16,67%
Both managed locally and received from an external authority	16,67%
Don't know	25,00%
Not applicable	20,83%
No response	12,50%

2.8.6 The use of REFEDS R&S entity category

The members of a national federation and users of EGI (Checking) or EUDATA (B2ACCESS) were asked on the use of REFEDS R&S entity category. We are not aware of any user in the Czech Republic or any entity planning to use it.

	Responses
No	16,67%

Yes	4,17%
Yes, in less than 1 year	0,00%
Yes, in 1 to 2 years	0,00%
Yes, in more than 2 years	0,00%
Don't know	29,17%
Not applicable	37,50%
No response	12,50%

2.9 FAIR Services

2.9.1 Availability of search for research data

An important feature for FAIR data is the service of the search for research data. The survey shows only one-third of the participants have this service up and running. However, more than 30% of them are working on the feature or at least consider the implementation, for example:

“We provide metadata - laboratory logbook search and a search in the database. However, not fulltext search is available, neither envisaged within < 3 years.”

“The organization has its own system for data and metadata management. The system is mainly used for collaboration with the partners internally. No data are opened for access using the system now. The system has a feature for data search.”

“We have this search feature but it is not applicable for the clinical trial data due to personal protection and privacy issues.”

	Responses
This feature is fully implemented.	29,17%
This feature is in the implementation phase.	12,50%
We are working on or have a theoretical concept for this feature.	20,83%
We have not considered this feature yet.	8,33%
Not applicable	20,83%
No response	8,33%

2.9.2 Data provenance information

The survey shows that almost one-half of the participants implement measures for ensuring documentation about the origin and the changes made in data (i.e. data provenance). For example:

“in clinical trials, it is called ‘audit trail’, we monitor all history of data change, identity of changer, and time of change”

However, some participants believe their procedures could be enhanced.

	Responses
Yes	45,83%
No	16,67%
Not applicable	33,33%
No response	4,17%

2.9.3 Data provenance measures

Among the participants having provenance information, we asked on implemented measures for documenting the origin and the changes made in data. Usual measures are version control and file integrity checks. Other measures, such as an audit trail, are less common but also in use in some participants.

	Responses
Version control	29,17%
File integrity checks (e.g. checksums, fixity checks)	29,17%
Other	8,33%
Not applicable	37,50%
No response	4,17%

2.9.4 FAIR policies

Some organisations have developed regulations related to their work processes, whereas other organisations have not. We investigated the existence of informal or formal regulations or publicly available policies that address several aspects.

	Usual policy
Open Access Publications	No or not mandatory
Research data management (RDM)	Usually no or not formal nor complex
Open research data	Usually no or not formal nor complex
Long-term availability of research data	Usually yes, sometimes informal
Compliance of data to the FAIR principles	Often yes, usually informal or needing enhancements
Publication of data in a repository	Roughly one half yes
Publication of data in a certified repository	Usually no
Other (please, specify)	For example policies on data capturing

2.9.5 Availability of search for metadata

An important feature for FAIR data is the service of the search for metadata. The survey shows the metadata search is usually implemented. The particular implementations vary:

“Partly implemented, enhancements planned for the upgraded infrastructure in future (> 2 years). Search available within the device logbook and within the database metadata.”

“The organization has its own system for data and metadata management. The system is mainly used for collaboration with the partners internally. No data are opened for access using the system now. The system has the feature for metadata search.”

“It is possible, but we were not required for it”

“but it is not used in the context of clinical trials due to legal issues”

“We offer corpus selection based on the corpus metadata and selection of individual texts within the given corpus based on the text metadata, so hopefully, this is what you mean.”

	Responses
This feature is fully implemented.	50,00%
This feature is in the implementation phase.	4,17%
We are working on or have a theoretical concept for this feature.	16,67%
We have not considered this feature yet.	0,00%

Not applicable	20,83%
No response	8,33%

2.9.6 Standardized/controlled vocabularies for metadata

Use of standardized/controlled vocabularies for metadata should be enhanced – only 40 % of participants stated that they are using them. For example, MOLGENIS (<https://molgenis.github.io/>), bioschemas (e.g., <http://sdo-bioschemas-227516.appspot.com/BioSample>) or medical coding vocabulary are used.

	Responses
Yes	33,33%
No	25,00%
Not applicable	29,17%
No response	12,50%

2.9.7 Most important standardized/controlled vocabularies used in metadata

The most important standardized/controlled vocabularies in metadata mentioned by the survey participants are:

- MOLGENIS (<https://molgenis.github.io/>)
- International Mouse Phenotyping Resource of Standardised Screens (<https://www.mousephenotype.org/impress/>)
- ISSN, ISBN
- MedDRA, WHO DD, Theoretical CDISC standard
- chronology, find types, research types, personal and institutional names, administrative regions, data/document types
- ELSST – European Language Social Science Thesaurus (<https://elsst.ukdataservice.ac.uk/>)

2.9.8 Language of metadata

Our survey shows, that metadata are provided only in Czech or English. More than half of the participants provide 100% of the metadata in English, almost 30% of participants provide all the metadata in Czech.

Language	Percent of metadata in the language						No response
	0%	1–25 %	26–50 %	51–75 %	76–99 %	100%	

Czech	4,17%	12,50%	0,00%	0,00%	8,33%	8,33%	41,67%
Slovak	12,50%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	41,67%
English	0,00%	8,33%	0,00%	4,17%	8,33%	33,33%	41,67%
German	12,50%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	41,67%
French	12,50%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	41,67%
Italian	12,50%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	41,67%
Dutch	12,50%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	41,67%
Other	12,50%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	41,67%

2.9.9 Certifications/audits of repositories

In our survey, we asked the participants whether they completed any certifications or audits relevant for repositories between 2015–2019. The results show that only very few respondents have the certification or are preparing for the certification process.

	Yes	No, but in preparation	No	No response
Core Trust Seal (CTS)	4,17%	4,17%	54,17%	37,50%
Data Seal of Approval (DSA)	4,17%	0,00%	58,33%	37,50%
World Data System (WDS)	0,00%	0,00%	62,50%	37,50%
ISO 16363 certification	0,00%	4,17%	58,33%	37,50%
Nestor Seal	0,00%	0,00%	62,50%	37,50%
Digital Repository Audit Method Based on Risk Assessment (DRAMBORA)	0,00%	0,00%	62,50%	37,50%
Trustworthy Repositories Audit & Certification (TRAC)	0,00%	0,00%	62,50%	37,50%

2.9.10 Level of content curation

An important part of FAIR services is a curation of the contents of repositories. Our survey shows that one-half of the participants do not do curation of the contents. If curation is done, it is usually only the basic curation (basic metadata, simple checks of data). On the other hand, almost 37% of respondents stated they are doing data level curation, including migration of data formats and advanced care of deposited data.

	Responses
We distribute the content as deposited.	33,33%
We perform basic curation (e.g. brief checking, addition of basic metadata or documentation).	29,17%
We perform enhanced curation (e.g. conversion to new formats, enhancement of documentation).	12,50%
We perform data-level curation (all changes made above and additional editing of deposited data for accuracy).	20,83%
No response	37,50%

2.9.11 Data FAIRness self-estimate

In the survey, we let the respondents self-evaluate (estimate) how FAIR are their data holdings. According to their opinions, they consider their data FAIR or on good direction to fulfil FAIR requirements although being aware of some limitations, for example: *“Within managed data, FAIR principles are largely implemented, but limitations lie mainly on the part of data suppliers. A major shift, especially with regard to interoperability and reusability, would require more emphasis on providing primary (raw) data directly from researchers, but for which we have limited options (both technical and in competences).”*

	Responses
Very much	16,67%
Somewhat	50,00%
Not very much	0,00%
Not at all	0,00%
Not applicable	0,00%
No response	33,33%

2.9.12 Machine-readable data catalogue

Among the survey participants, there is in general good coverage of data catalogues available in machine-readable formats although details differ case by case:

“It is different in each biobank. Usually, they have a database with GUI. A connector is a tool in a pilot phase working with structured data gathered from biobank database...”

”Difficult of say, it depends on the type of data, for some kind data yes, for some no”

“all of the study datasets have their own data dictionary”

“All metadata on research data and data stored in the database are available via open API”

“Accessible only to project members.”

Only 15 % of participants have not implemented this feature and are not planning to implement it in the foreseen future.

	Responses
This feature is fully implemented.	29,17%
This feature is in the implementation phase.	4,17%
We are working on or have a theoretical concept for this feature.	16,67%
We have not considered this feature yet.	8,33%
Not applicable	4,17%
No response	37,50%

2.9.13 Researchers unique identifiers

According to our survey, roughly 35% of the participants are not using any type of unique identifiers for researchers to clearly identify and distinguish natural persons in metadata. Other are using ORCID, ResearcherID or other identifiers such as custom own IDs.

The technical details differ depending on the specific needs or special requirements such as pseudonymization of data; for example:

“IDs internally used are replaced by new pseudonyms relevant only for the data set”

“All of the data are supplemented with relevant persistent identifiers for cataloguing of books and articles, in particular ID’s of Czech National authorities set (complementary with VIAF or Wikidata etc.), ISSN, ISBN, Czech National Bibliography ID etc.”

“Internal [institutional] accounts connected with email accounts.”

	Responses
Not applicable	8,33%
No	20,83%
Yes, ORCID	16,67%
Yes, ResearcherID	12,50%
Yes, other (please specify)	16,67%
No response	37,50%

2.10 Repositories Parameters

2.10.1 Type of digital data archived in repositories

Investigation of data types in the repositories showed that the most common data types are numeric data followed by texts and images. Video and software are also common. Geospatial, audio and 3D data are less common. None of the respondents is archiving interactive resources. Bibliographic and database records were also present: *“Bibliographical records are primarily metadata about existing publications, not the data itself. They can be supplemented by a link to the online accessible version of the processed document (web, repository, digital library).”*

	Responses
Numeric	54,17%
Text	37,50%
Still image	25,00%
Geospatial	8,33%
Audio	8,33%

Video	16,67%
Software	16,67%
Interactive resource	4,17%
3D	8,33%
Other (please specify)	8,33%
No response	37,50%

2.10.2 Number of datasets accessible online

In the survey, we were interested in how many datasets have participants accessible online.

A dataset is a logical collection of one or more files which is described by a metadata scheme, however, some respondents were not sure how to divide data to the dataset:

“The database contains approx. 20.000 experimental discharges, each containing up to 1.500 signals. Depending on the matter of interest, the datasets can be considered either as the individual discharges or as a subset of selected signals across different discharges.”

“Our data consists of 2 main (so called contemporary bibliography and retrospective bibliography) and 3 minor datasets, mostly in MARC21 or MARC21 for authorities format. ‘Contemporary’ bibliography can be further divided into the specific logical datasets, but the metadata scheme is the same. Retrospective bibliography in RETROBI system (digitised card catalogue) has its own proprietary data format which is quite similar to MARC21 standard.”

The particular number of datasets differed significantly among the participants from units, tens and hundreds of datasets to tens of thousands to much higher numbers, for example:

“1 type, but it is lots of data, roughly 700 000 parameters, or 120 datasets plus big dataset as control”

“Ten of thousands of datasets varying in volume from single files to thousands of files and including metadata descriptions.”

“10⁶”

2.11 Effective Sharing of Data

2.11.1 Characteristics of frequently reused datasets

We asked our respondents to think about datasets that are reused frequently and decide on characteristics that they think to be important for frequent reuse of datasets. We received a variety of thoughts on properties making datasets popular:

“The datasets include both raw and processed data, both 1-D data series, 2-D images, and videos.”

“Machine-readable format?”

“Easy way to download them and display them”

“Common standard, unified data structure.”

“recent simulations are used more frequently”

“New simulation models”

“For individual user: Well-organised metadata with well-structured vocabularies; correct geospatial and chronological description; minimum accessibility restrictions (open licence).

For other infrastructures / applications / institutions: Persistency, data and metadata format, availability via API, applied standards and ontology.”

“research topic”

“comparability (international, in time or both), representativity, interesting topic, data and metadata quality”

“In the case of individual users, there are very conservative uses, namely, in particular, the search for material for their own publication and research activities, but not mass harvesting. For institutional users, on the other hand, the inherent interoperability of systems and the provision of logical links between our systems and the recipient of the data (e.g. museums, heritage institutions) is important.”

In summary, FAIR principles, such as availability, use of standards, machine-readable formats, findability, persistence etc. seems to be identified as characteristics making datasets reused more often.

2.11.2 Users' concerns about data sharing

Some researchers or organisations are reluctant to share and/or publish data, others are not. We asked, how concerned are customers/depositors about several aspects of data sharing. We received a variety of opinions, for example:

- Lack of control over the usage of data
 - *“Yes, mainly consistency of the data interpretation.”*
 - *“They agree after publication”*
 - *“Not applicable.”*
 - *“not concerned, we guarantee only customers will access the data”*
 - *“no”*
 - *“Moderately (varies a lot)”*
 - *“Yes, but not so important.”*
 - *“data must be secured”*
- The effort of preparing the data for publication
 - *“Yes, time demanding for the scientific staff, additional resources needed among the scientific as well as technical staff.”*
 - *“It is the main reason for generating data”*
 - *“a lot”*
 - *“a little concerned”*
 - *“no”*
 - *“Very”*
 - *“Yes, very important.”*
 - *“data must be secured”*
- Doubts about the depositor's benefit of sharing data
 - *“Depending on the depositor.”*
 - *“No problems”*
 - *“not concerned, we guarantee only customers will access the data”*
 - *“no”*

- *“Moderately”*
 - *“Yes, important.”*
 - *“data must be secured”*
- The competitive disadvantage when sharing
 - *“Yes, related to the data not fully exploited by the staff and collaborators yet.”*
 - *“After publication”*
 - *“Not a problem”*
 - *“not concerned, we guarantee only customers will access the data”*
 - *“partly”*
 - *“Moderately”*
 - *“Yes, important.”*
 - *“data must be secured”*
- Data protection
 - *“Data shall not be made available to un-reliable entities and states.”*
 - *“After publication”*
 - *“No problem.”*
 - *“a little concerned”*
 - *“partly”*
 - *“Low”*
 - *“We do not accept personal data.”*
 - *“data must be secured”*
- Intellectual property (e.g. copyright)
 - *“Yes, related to the new developments and securing the protection of public investments.”*
 - *“It must be said, who and from which deposit data are taken...”*
 - *“Not a problem”*
 - *“a little concerned”*
 - *“no”*
 - *“Moderately”*
 - *“Yes, copyrights at data are sometimes unclear.”*
 - *“data must be secured”*
- Other (please, specify)
 - *“Sharing datasets obtained from several infrastructures, that includes a mix of policies and different physical locations of the data, difficult to manage without a dedicated effort.”*

We also received some other comments relevant to the topic:

“Biobanks usually do not offer such services.”

“The results obtained on the basis of economic contracts are the property of the client and are freely available only with his consent.”

“I would say that the most widespread concern among the humanities researchers is the competitive disadvantage when sharing (typically not justified, just felt as such).”

“Non-negligible effort to publish data is required. Raw data are not published, customers would not be able to correctly reconstruct them. Only subset of final data is published for outreach and educational purposes.”

2.12 Services for EOSC

2.12.1 Research disciplines benefiting most from EOSC

We asked our participants on their opinion what research disciplines they expect to benefit mostly from EOSC.

The most is expected in STEM disciplines, especially in Natural Sciences. Social sciences and humanities are expected to benefit less from EOSC.

	Responses
Natural Sciences	58,33%
Engineering and Technology	29,17%
Medical and Health Sciences	20,83%
Agricultural Sciences	16,67%
Social Sciences	8,33%
Humanities	12,50%
Other (please specify)	8,33%
No response	16,67%

2.12.2 Audience of services by scientific disciplines

According to our survey, our participants provide services primarily to Natural Sciences. Other disciplines are handled by minority of the participants.

	Responses
Natural Sciences	66,67%
Engineering and Technology	29,17%
Medical and Health Sciences	29,17%
Agricultural Sciences	16,67%
Social Sciences	16,67%
Humanities	16,67%
Other (please specify)	8,33%
No response	8,33%

2.12.3 Presence of organisations in an official roadmaps

Three quarters of the participants are present in the national roadmap, one half in ESFRI roadmap. Almost 10% is present in other roadmaps such as EUROfusion consortium (EURATOM) or IMPC. One member of e-INFRA CZ also represents Czech Republic in the PRACE ESFRI.

	Responses
Don't know	0,00%
No	0,00%
Yes, national	70,83%
Yes, ESFRI	50,00%
Yes, other	8,33%
No response	8,33%

2.12.4 Transnational organisation/federation offering Service Level Agreements

We asked our participants whether they are in a transnational organisation or federation that offers Service Level Agreements (SLAs) or similar contracts that are also binding for their organisations. Only 35% responded that they are.

Agreements are, for example:

“CzBI infrastructure is not bound by an SLA of a transnational organization, however some of its partners/facilities are part of the Euro-BioImaging organization, which does offer SLA.”

“We are a member of ECRIN-ERIC. Joint project is covered by a contract, but not by SLAs.”

“EuroNanoLab”

“<http://plus.aginfra.eu/>”

	Responses
Yes	33,33%
No	37,50%
Don't know	16,67%

No response	12,50%
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2.12.5 Integration of data/services into EOSC

We asked our participants whether their organisations are part of or related to another organisation which facilitates integrating their data and services into EOSC. Only 30% of respondents were part of / related to such an organization. The organizations were: IMPC, INFRANFORTIER, AGINFRA+, CERN, and CESSDA ERIC.

	Responses
Yes	29,17%
No	45,83%
Don't know	12,50%
No response	12,50%

2.12.6 Participation in selected EOSC-related European organizations

We asked our respondents on participation in the following EOSC-related European organisations. Only e-INFRA CZ, the national e-infrastructure, is participating in all of them, representing the Czech Republic.

	Responses
Don't know	8,33%
None	45,83%
EGI	8,33%
EUDAT	4,17%
PRACE (Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe)	4,17%
Other (respondents mentioned either thematic research infrastructures, clusters of them, or participation in international organization like CERN, EMBL, EuroHPC, GEANT, but not explicitly EOSC-related ones)	29,17%
No response	16,67%

2.12.6.1 National/international level of participation

The respondents participating in a European organization were asked on the level of participation. All of them are participating on an international level if applicable.

	Responses
National level	0,00%
International level	33,33%
Not applicable	12,50%
No response	54,17%

2.12.7 Collaboration on hardware producement

We asked in the survey whether the participants are collaborating with other organizations if producing hardware. The results show collaboration up to 20%.

	Responses
No	16,67%
Yes, but just informing each other	12,50%
Yes, we do a joint tender	4,17%
Not applicable	58,33%
No response	8,33%

2.12.7.1 National/international level of collaboration

The respondents collaborating with other organizations on the production of hardware were asked on level of participation. More cooperation is international than national only.

	Responses
National level	4,17%
International level	12,50%
Not applicable	29,17%
No response	54,17%

2.12.8 Obstacles of collaboration on services or hardware procurement

We were asking our participants what are the major obstacles that prohibit them to collaborate on service or hardware procurement.

	Responses
Legal aspects	16,67%
Timing problems (different availability of budget)	8,33%
No clear benefit	29,17%
Other (please specify)	12,50%
No response	50,00%

Among other reasons was an especially different aim of the organization when procurement is out of the scope of their activities or the lack of benefits from such a collaboration.

2.12.9 Experience with the international service tenders

We asked our respondents on experience with the international service tenders, e.g. cloud service provisioning. The vast majority of them have no experience.

	Responses
Yes	12,50%
No	70,83%
No response	16,67%

2.12.10 Cross-border services

According to our survey, all the participants, where applicable, are providing their service cross-border.

	Responses
Yes	83,33%
No	0,00%
Not applicable	8,33%
No response	8,33%

2.12.11 Services differentiation between national and international users

In our survey, we asked the participants whether they differentiate their services in access rights or extent (e.g. capacity available) between national and international users. The results show that the vast majority provide their services equally to all the users. However, some providers apply some limitations, for example: “National users can have also local access. International users have only access via grid” or “Foreign users may be a subject to an additional access approval.”

	Responses
Not applicable	0,00%
No, all users are treated equally	79,17%
Yes, international users are not accepted	0,00%
Yes, international users are not allowed without a clear link/relation with national users	8,33%
Yes, national users are prioritized (specify, if possible)	4,17%
No response	8,33%

2.12.11.1 Major reasons for limiting international users

Main reasons for limiting international users are national or institutional policies. Less common are insufficient resources (funding).

	Responses
Official national policy	16,67%
Official policy of our organization	4,17%
Insufficient resources (funding)	8,33%
Other (please specify)	8,33%
No response	75,00%

2.12.12 Expected/wanted EOSC help

At the end of our survey, we asked the survey participant where they expect/want EOSC to help. The most expected is a more trusted environment and removal of differentiation of (national level) policies. Other reasons were, for example:

“help with data archiving/storing - provide hardware, metadata gathering and sharing - GUIs”

“Provide funding for implementing the FAIR data principles”

”Provide access to additional hardware resources and funds to integrate them to the organization's own resources.”

“We look forward to EOSC to help with homogenising the e-infrastructures' related policies”

	Responses
Providing funding to cover the cost of international users	16,67%
Removing policy differences (at national levels)	25,00%
Providing more trusted environment (e.g. identity vetting)	37,50%
Other (please specify)	12,50%
No response	45,83%

3 Survey Results: Funders

3.1 Funding Rules

3.1.1 What the organization funds

The participants were asked what type of costs they are funding. Most of them fund all types of common costs, project based resources (for example, “local office” – material and services related to project management) are funded by only one third of them.

	Responses
Human resources	90,91%
Hardware	72,73%
Software	72,73%
Capital expenditure (capex) at large	81,82%
Operational expenditure (opex) at large	100,00%
Project based resources	36,36%
Other (please specify)	0,00%
No response	0,00%

3.1.2 Rules for granting funds for e-infrastructures or research infrastructures

We asked about the existence of granting rules based on several aspects. The vast majority of them have rules on discipline of the infrastructure’s users, less than 10% of them apply selection by a competitive process.

	Responses
Discipline of the infrastructure’s users	90,91%
Geographical location of the infrastructure's users	0,00%
Selection by a competitive process	0,00%
Affiliation of the infrastructure’s users	9,09%
Not applicable	0,00%
Other (please specify)	0,00%
No response	0,00%

3.1.3 Requirements on providing the cost information about the offered services

The respondents were asked whether they require infrastructures to provide the cost information about the services they offer. Only one responded requires this information for all grants.

	Responses
Yes, always	9,09%
Yes, for some grants	0,00%
No, but (maybe) in the future	0,00%
No	0,00%
Not applicable	90,91%
No response	0,00%

3.1.4 Maintenance of a roadmap of the funded infrastructures

The participants were asked whether they maintain a roadmap of the infrastructures they fund and how many years the roadmaps typically cover. The results show it is not common, only one funding organization is aligning its roadmap to the national roadmap.

	Responses
No	90,91%
Yes, aligned to a European roadmap.	0,00%
Yes, aligned to a national roadmap.	9,09%
Yes, we maintain a roadmap according to our own specifications.	0,00%
No response	0,00%

3.1.5 Users support as eligible cost

The respondents were asked whether they allow infrastructures who receive grants to spend funding on user support. Only one participant explicitly states that the user support is eligible cost.

	Responses
We explicitly offer funding for user support	0,00%
Grant regulations allow for spending funds on user support	9,09%
Grant regulations prohibit spending funds on user support	0,00%
Not applicable	90,91%
Other (please specify)	0,00%
No response	0,00%

3.1.6 Organisations imposing rules for funding on (internal) grant recipients concerning the various aspects

The participants of the survey were asked about the existence and type of requirements of the recipients of their grants in several areas related to Open Sciences. All of them apply optional regulations in all the asked areas of Open Science.

	No encouraged regulation but optional	Mandatory, for some grants	Mandatory, not for all applicable grants	Mandatory, for all grants	No response
Open Access Publications	100,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Data Management Plans	100,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Open Research Data	100,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Long-Term Availability of Research Data	100,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Compliance of Data to the FAIR Principles	100,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Compliance of Data to the FAIR Principles	100,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%
Publishing Data in a Repository	100,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%	0,00%

3.2 Policies

3.2.1 Status of organizations with regard to the Commission Recommendation (EU) 2018/790 on access to and preservation of scientific information

The recommendation sums up the current policy of European Commission towards Open Access to scientific information. The aim was to describe the overall policy of the institutions towards Open Access to scientific information. By scientific information the recommendation means both publications and data.

We collected no response to this question in our survey among research funders, but as seen from the previous answer, the recommendations are true “recommendations”, i.e. they are not mandatory. The discussion about more strict application of the recommendation is only starting.